

*Article***On The Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Calculus**Necati Olgun¹, and Hatice Kahraman^{2,*}¹ Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep University, Turkey 1; olgun@gantep.edu.tr² Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep University, Turkey 1; kahramannhatiice@gmail.com* Correspondence: kahramannhatiice@gmail.com*Received:* 04 05, 2024; *Accepted:* 04 10, 2024.

Abstract: Depending on the geometric isometry (AH-Isometry), it has been proven that every Neutrosophic real function is equivalent to three real functions. Then, the foundation of the symbolic 2-plithogenic calculus was established, where new definitions of symbolic 2-plithogenic integration and symbolic 2-plithogenic differentiation were introduced, along with some illustrative examples. Following that, definitions for the symbolic 2-plithogenic gamma function and symbolic 2-plithogenic beta function were presented to pave the way towards achieving the desired goal, which is symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional calculus.

Keywords: Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Real Function, Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Integration, Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Derivative, Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Gamma Function and Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Beta Function.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophy is a new branch of philosophy concerns with the indeterminacy in all areas of life and science. It has become a useful tool in generalizing many classical systems such as equations [1,9], number theory [2,3], topology [4,5], linear spaces [6,10], modules [4,5], and ring of matrices [7,8].

In the literature, we find many studies about neutrosophic calculus, where some definitions and properties were presented about neutrosophic real functions and numbers [10]. The neutrosophic real functions with one variable were defined only in a special case [11], as follows:

Recently, Abobala and Hatip, have presented the concept of two-dimensional AH-isometry to study the correspondence between neutrosophic plane $R(I) \times R(I)$ and the classical module $R^2 \times R^2$. Also, the one-dimensional AH-isometry between $R(I)$ and $R \times R$. This isometry was useful in defining inner products and norms [10], ordering [9], and neutrosophic geometrical shapes [10].

In [12], the concept of symbolic n-plithogenic algebraic structures was proposed by Smarandache, then it was used on a wide range by many researchers to generalize classical algebraic structures such as modules [13], spaces [14-15], equations [16], and number theory [17-18]. In [19], the concept of symbolic 2-plithogenic matrices was presented with many applications in the theory of algebraic equations and representing functions. Laterally, symbolic 3-plithogenic matrices and 4-plithogenic matrices were studied from many algebraic sides, especially those which are related to the diagonalization problem [20].

In this work, we use the one-dimensional AH-isometry to turn the general case of symbolic 2-plithogenic neutrosophic real functions with one variable into three classical real functions so we

will go from $2 - SP_R$ space into $R \times R \times R$ space. The definitions of symbolic 2-plithogenic integration and symbolic 2-plithogenic differentiation were introduced.

Following that, definitions for the symbolic 2-plithogenic Gamma function and symbolic 2-plithogenic Beta function were presented to pave the way towards symbolic 2-plithogenic Fractional calculus.

2. Terminologies

We present here some basic definitions and axioms of neutrosophic logic and refined neutrosophic logic.

Definition 2.1. [21]: Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set A is an object having the form $\{x, (\mu_A(x), \delta_A(x), \gamma_A(x)): x \in X\}$, where $\mu_A(x)$, $\delta_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ represent the degree of membership, the degree of indeterminacy, and the degree of non-membership respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

Definition 2.2.[22]: Let K be a field, the neutrosophic field generated by $\langle K \cup I \rangle$ which is denoted by $K(I) = \langle K \cup I \rangle$.

Definition 2.3. [23]: Classical neutrosophic number has the form $a + bI$ where a, b are real or complex numbers and I is the indeterminacy such that $0 \cdot I = 0$ and $I^2 = I$ which results that $I^n = I$ for all positive integers n .

Definition 2.4.[24] Let $R(I) = \{a + bI; a, b \in R\}$ where $I^2 = I$ be the neutrosophic field of reals. The one-dimensional isometry (AH-Isometry) is defined as follows: [49]

$$T: R(I) \rightarrow R \times R; T(a + bI) = (a, a + b)$$

Remark 2.5. [24]

T is an algebraic isomorphism between two rings, it has the following properties:

- 1) T is bijective.
- 2) T preserves addition and multiplication, i.e.:
- 3) Since T is bijective, then it is invertible by:

$$T^{-1}: R \times R \rightarrow R(I); T^{-1}(a, b) = a + (b - a)I$$

- 4) T preserves distances, i.e.:

$$\|T(AB)\| = T(\|AB\|)$$

Definition 2.6. [25]: Let $f: R(I) \rightarrow R(I); f = f(X)$ and $X = x + yI \in R(I)$ the f is called a neutrosophic real function with one neutrosophic variable.

a neutrosophic real function $f(X)$ written as follows:

$$f(X) = f(x + yI) = f(x) + I[f(x + y) - f(x)]$$

Definition 2.7.[25]: Let R be a ring, the symbolic 2-plithogenic ring is defined as follows:

$$2 - SPR = \{a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2; a_i \in R, I_1^2 = I_1, I_2^2 = I_2, I_1 \times I_2 = I_{\max(1,2)} = I_2\}.$$

Smarandache has defined algebraic operations on $2 - SP_R$ as follows:

Addition:

$$[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2] + [b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2] = (a_0 + b_0) + (a_1 + b_1)I_1 + (a_2 + b_2)I_2.$$

Multiplication:

$$[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2] \cdot [b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2] = (a_0b_0) + (a_0b_1 + a_1b_0 + a_1b_1)I_1 + (a_0b_2 + a_1b_2 + a_2b_0 + a_2b_1 + a_2b_2)I_2.$$

Definition 2.8. Let $2 - SP_R = \{a + bI_1 + cI_2; a, b, c \in R\}$ where

$$I_1^2 = I_1, I_2^2 = I_2 \text{ and } I_1I_2 = I_2I_1 = I_2$$

Be the symbolic 2-plithogenic field of reals. The symbolic 2-plithogenic isometry (AH-Isometry) is defined as follows:

$$T: 2 - SP_R \rightarrow R \times R \times R; T(a + bI_1 + cI_2) = (a, a + b + c, a + c)$$

Remark 2.9.

1) T is bijective, then it is invertible by:

$$T^{-1}: R \times R \times R \rightarrow 2 - SP_R; T^{-1}(a, b, c) = a + (b - c)I_1 + (c - a)I_2$$

2) T preserves distances, i.e.:

$$\|T(AB)\| = T(\|AB\|)$$

3. Symbolic 2-plithogenic Calculus

3.1 Symbolic 2-plithogenic Real Function

Definition 3.1.1. Let $f: 2 - SP_R \rightarrow 2 - SP_R$; $f = f(X(I_1, I_2))$ and $X = x + yI_1 + zI_2 \in 2 - SP_R$ the f is called the symbolic 2-plithogenic real function with the symbolic 2-plithogenic variable, written as follows:

$$f(X(I_1, I_2)) = f(x + yI_1 + zI_2) = f(x) + (f(x + y + z) - f(x + z))I_1 + (f(x + z) - f(x))I_2$$

Theorem 3.1.2. Any symbolic 2-plithogenic real function into three classical real functions, i.e., to the classical Euclidean plane $R \times R \times R$.

Proof.

Let $f(X(I_1, I_2)) = f(x + yI_1 + zI_2) = f(x) + (f(x + y + z) - f(x + z))I_1 + (f(x + z) - f(x))I_2$ a symbolic 2-plithogenic real function.

Now, Using the one-dimensional AH-isometry, we have.

$$T(f(X(I_1, I_2))) = T(f(x) + (f(x + y + z) - f(x + z))I_1 + (f(x + z) - f(x))I_2), \text{ then.}$$

$(f_1, f_2, f_3) = (f(x), f(x + y + z) - f(x + z), f(x + z) - f(x))$, then, we have.

$$\begin{cases} f_1 = f(x) \\ f_2 = f(x + y + z) - f(x + z) \\ f_3 = f(x + z) - f(x) \end{cases}$$

The functions $f(x), f(x + y + z) - f(x + z), f(x + z) - f(x)$ are three real functions.

Example 3.1.3. Let $2 - SP_R$ be the symbolic 2-plithogenic field of reals, we have:

1. $f(X(I_1, I_2)) = e^{x+yI_1+zI_2}$
 $= e^x + (e^{x+y+z} - e^{x+z})I_1 + (e^{x+z} - e^x)I_2$
2. $f(X(I_1, I_2)) = \ln(x + yI_1 + zI_2)$
 $= \ln(x) + (\ln(x + y + z) - \ln(x + z))I_1 + (\ln(x + z) - \ln(x))I_2$, where
 $x + yI_1 + zI_2 > 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$.
3. $f(X(I_1, I_2)) = \sqrt{x + yI_1 + zI_2}$
 $= \sqrt{x} + (\sqrt{x + y + z} - \sqrt{x + z})I_1 + (\sqrt{x + z} - \sqrt{x})I_2$, where
 $x + yI_1 + zI_2 \geq 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$.
4. $f(X(I_1, I_2)) = \sin(x + yI_1 + zI_2)$
 $= \sin(x) + (\sin(x + y + z) - \sin(x + z))I_1 + (\sin(x + z) - \sin(x))I_2$

3.2 The Derivative of Symbolic 2-plithogenic Real Functions on $2 - SP_R$.

Definition 3.2.1. Let $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ a symbolic 2-plithogenic function on $2 - SP_R$, the we define a derivative of a symbolic 2-plithogenic function $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ as follows:

$$f'_{X(I_1, I_2)}(X(I_1, I_2)) = f'_x(x) + (f'_{x+y}(x + y + z) - f'_{x+z}(x + z))I_1 + (f'_{x+z}(x + z) - f'_x(x))I_2$$

Examples 3.2.2.

$$1. e^{X(I_1, I_2)} = e^{x+yI_1+zI_2} = e^x + (e^{x+y+z} - e^{x+z})I_1 + (e^{x+z} - e^x)I_2$$

we have:

$$f'_{X(I_1, I_2)}(X(I_1, I_2)) = e^x + (e^{x+y+z} - e^{x+z})I_1 + (e^{x+z} - e^x)I_2 = e^{x+yI_1+zI_2}.$$

$$2. f(X(I_1, I_2)) = \ln(x + yI_1 + zI_2) \\ = \ln(x) + (\ln(x + y + z) - \ln(x + z))I_1 + (\ln(x + z) - \ln(x))I_2, \text{ where} \\ x + yI_1 + zI_2 > 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2 .$$

We have.

$$f'_{X(I_1, I_2)}(X(I_1, I_2)) = \frac{1}{x} + \left(\frac{1}{x + y + z} - \frac{1}{x + z}\right)I_1 + \left(\frac{1}{x + z} - \frac{1}{x}\right)I_2$$

$$3. f(X(I_1, I_2)) = \sin(x + yI_1 + zI_2) \\ = \sin(x) + (\sin(x + y + z) - \sin(x + z))I_1 + (\sin(x + z) - \sin(x))I_2$$

We have.

$$f'_{X(I_1, I_2)}(X(I_1, I_2)) = \cos(x) + (\cos(x + y + z) - \cos(x + z))I_1 + (\cos(x + z) - \cos(x))I_2 \\ = \cos X(I_1, I_2).$$

3.3 The Integral of Symbolic 2-plithogenic Functions on $\mathbf{2} - SP_R$.

Definition 3.3.1. Let $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ a symbolic 2-plithogenic function on $\mathbf{2} - SP_R$, the we define a integration of a symbolic 2-plithogenic function $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ as follows:

$$\int f(X(I_1, I_2)) dX(I_1, I_2) = F(X(I_1, I_2)) = F(x) + [F(x + y + z) - F(x + z)]I_1 + [F(x + z) - F(x)]I_2.$$

Examples 3.3.2.

$$1. f(X(I_1, I_2)) = e^{X(I_1, I_2)}. \text{ We have.}$$

$$\int e^{x+yI_1+zI_2} dX \\ = \int e^x dx + \left[\int e^{x+y+z} d(x + y + z) - \int e^{x+z} d(x + z) \right] I_1 \\ + \left[\int e^{x+z} d(x + z) - \int e^x dx \right] I_2 \\ = e^x + (e^{x+y+z} - e^{x+z})I_1 + (e^{x+z} - e^x)I_2 + a + bI_1 + cI_2 \\ = e^{x+yI_1+zI_2} + a + bI_1 + cI_2$$

wherea, b, c are constests.

$$2. f(X(I_1, I_2)) = \cos(x + yI_1 + zI_2) \text{ we have}$$

$$\int \cos(x + yI_1 + zI_2) dX(I_1, I_2) \\ = \int \cos(x) dx + \left[\int \cos(x + y + z) d(x + y + z) - \int \cos(x + z) d(x + z) \right] I_1 \\ + \left[\int \cos(x + z) d(x + z) - \int \cos(x) dx \right] I_2 \\ = \sin(x) + (\sin(x + y + z) - \sin(x + z))I_1 + (\sin(x + z) - \sin(x))I_2 + a \\ + bI_1 + cI_2 = \sin(x + yI_1 + zI_2) + a + bI_1 + cI_2$$

wherea, b, c are constests.

3.4 The Definite Integration of Symbolic 2-plithogenic Functions on $\mathbf{2} - SP_R$.

Definition 2.4.1.

Let $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ a symbolic 2-plithogenic function on $\mathbf{2} - SP_R$, we define the definite integration of a symbolic 2-plithogenic function $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ as follows:

$$\int_{a+bl_1+cl_2}^{d+el_1+fl_2} f(X(I_1, I_2))dX(I_1, I_2)$$

$$= \int_a^d f(x)dx + \left[\int_{a+b+c}^{d+e+f} f(x+y+z)d(x+y+z) - \int_{a+c}^{d+f} f(x+z)d(x+z) \right] I_1$$

$$+ \left[\int_{a+c}^{d+f} f(x+z)d(x+z) - \int_a^d f(x)dx \right] I_2$$

Example 3.4.2.

$$1. J = \int_{0+0I_1+0I_2}^{1+I_1+I_2} e^{X(I_1, I_2)} dX(I_1, I_2)$$

$$= \int_0^1 e^x dx + \left[\int_0^3 e^{(x+y+z)} d((x+y+z)) - \int_1^2 e^{(x+z)} d(x+z) \right] I_1$$

$$+ \left[\int_1^2 e^{(x+z)} d((x+y+z)) - \int_0^1 e^x dx \right] I_2$$

$$= [e^x]_0^1 + [[e^{(x+y+z)}]_0^3 - [e^{(x+z)}]_1^2] I_1 + [[e^{(x+z)}]_1^2 - [e^x]_0^1] I_2$$

$$J = (e - 1) + ((e^3 - 1) - (e^2 - e))I_1 + ((e^2 - e) - (e - 1))I_2.$$

4.1 Useful Symbolic 2-plithogenic Functions

Definition 4.1.1.The most basic interpretation of the symbolic 2-plithogenicGamma function is simply the generalization of the symbolic 2-plithogenicfactorial for all symbolic 2-plithogenicreal numbers.

We define a symbolic 2-plithogenicGamma function as follows:

$$\Gamma(Z(I_1, I_2)) = \Gamma(z_1 + z_2I_1 + z_3I_2)$$

$$= \Gamma(z_1) + (\Gamma(z_1 + z_2 + z_3) - \Gamma(z_1 + z_3))I_1 + (\Gamma(z_1 + z_3) - \Gamma(z_1))I_2$$

$$= \int_0^\infty (t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2)^{(z_1+z_2I_1+z_3I_2)-1} e^{-(t_1+t_2I_1+t_3I_2)} d(t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2)$$

Remark 4.1.2.

$$1. \Gamma(1 + 0I_1 + 0I_2) = \Gamma(1) + (\Gamma(1) - \Gamma(1))I_1 + (\Gamma(1) - \Gamma(1))I_2 = 1$$

And we can proof in this way,

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(1) &= \Gamma(1 + 0I_1 + 0I_2) = \int_0^\infty (t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2)^{1-1} e^{-(t_1+t_2I_1+t_3I_2)} d(t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2) \\ &= \int_0^\infty e^{-(t_1+t_2I_1+t_3I_2)} d(t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2) \\ &= \int_0^\infty e^{-t_1} d(t_1) + \left[\int_0^\infty e^{-(t_1+t_2+t_3)} d(t_1 + t_2 + t_3) - \int_0^\infty e^{-(t_1+t_3)} d((t_1 + t_3)) \right] I_1 \\ &\quad + \left[\int_0^\infty e^{-(t_1+t_3)} d(t_1 + t_3) - \int_0^\infty e^{-t_1} d(t_1) \right] I_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Gamma(1) = [-e^{-t_1}]_0^\infty + \left([-e^{-(t_1+t_2+t_3)}]_0^\infty - [-e^{-(t_1+t_3)}]_0^\infty \right) I_1 + \left([-e^{-(t_1+t_3)}]_0^\infty - [-e^{-t_1}]_0^\infty \right) I_2$$

$$\Gamma(1) = 1 + 0I_1 + 0I_2 = 1$$

In the same way we can proof,

1. $\Gamma(Z(I_1, I_2) + 1) = (Z(I_1, I_2))\Gamma(Z(I_1, I_2))$
2. $\Gamma(n + mI_1 + pI_2) = (n + mI_1 + pI_2)! ; n + mI_1 + pI_2 \in N(I_1, I_2)$

Definition 4.1.3.

Like the symbolic 2-plithogenicGamma function, the symbolic 2-plithogenicBeta function is defined by a definite symbolic 2-plithogenicintegral. Its definition is given by

$$\begin{aligned} B(P(I_1, I_2), Q(I_1, I_2)) &= B(p_1 + p_2I_1 + p_3I_2, q_1 + q_2I_1 + q_3I_2) \\ &= \int_0^1 (t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2)^{(p_1+p_2I_1+p_3I_2)-1} (1 - (t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2))^{(q_1+q_2I_1+q_3I_2)-1} d(t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2) \end{aligned}$$

The Beta function can also be defined in terms of the Gamma function:

$$B(P(I_1, I_2), Q(I_1, I_2)) = \frac{\Gamma(P(I_1, I_2)) \cdot \Gamma(Q(I_1, I_2))}{\Gamma((P(I_1, I_2)) + (Q(I_1, I_2)))}$$

3. Conclusion

Symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional calculus is a more generalized form of calculus. Unlike the symbolic 2-plithogenicinteger order calculus where operations are centered mainly at the symbolic 2-plithogenicintegers, fractional calculus considers every real symbolic 2-plithogenicnumber, $\nu(I_1, I_2)$. And as it has been briefly noted in this paper, the meaning and applications of this new type of calculus are quite comparable to those of the ordinary calculus, especially when gets closer and closer to a symbolic 2-plithogenicinteger. In the future, studying the symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional calculus became possible thanks to the definitions mentioned in the paper.

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